

RBP-ReguNet

Deliverable 6.2

Plan for the Integration of Gender Dimension

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1. Glossary Of Acronyms

Acronym	Full Concept
DC	Doctoral Candidate
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
GEDIP	Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Plan
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
MSCA	Marie-Sklodowska Curie Actions
RBP	RNA-Binding Proteins
R&I	Research and innovation

2. Introduction

2.1. Gender Equality, gender dimension, and Europe

First, it is necessary to establish some fundamental definitions of the key concepts that underlie the content of this deliverable document. The first concept we address is gender equality. **Gender** refers to sociocultural norms, identities, and relationships that shape behaviours, products, technologies, environments, and knowledge. Gender attitudes and behaviours are multifaceted and subject to change over time, influenced by factors such as education, age, socioeconomic status, cultural background, religious beliefs, and infrastructural conditions. **Gender equality**, therefore, represents a state where individuals of all genders are empowered to develop their personal abilities and make choices without the limitations imposed by rigid gender roles. It involves recognizing, valuing, and promoting equal consideration of the diverse behaviours, aspirations, and needs of both women and men. Additionally, we must consider the complementary **gender dimension**, which encompasses the biological characteristics as well as the social and cultural aspects, behaviours, and needs of individuals of all genders. Integrating the gender dimension is crucial for enhancing the societal relevance and quality of research and innovation (R&I). Within our research field, the consideration of the **sex dimension** is essential when designing and conducting experiments and analysing data. Sex refers to the biological attributes that distinguish females, males, and/or intersex individuals based on chromosomal complement, reproductive organs, specific hormones, or environmental factors affecting phenotypic traits expression in sexually reproducing organisms¹.

Incorporating the gender dimension into a project, entails analysing sex and/or gender factors throughout the entire research and innovation (R&I) process. This encompasses various stages, including establishing research priorities, defining concepts, formulating research questions, developing methodologies, collecting, and analysing sex/gender-disaggregated data, evaluating and reporting findings, and translating them into marketable products and innovations. The integration of the gender dimension holds significant value across multiple R&I fields. By considering potential sex and/or gender differences and addressing gender equality issues, it enhances research excellence, rigor, reproducibility, and creativity. Moreover, it fosters a comprehensive understanding of the needs, behaviours, and attitudes of all individuals, thereby increasing the societal relevance of research and innovation. Also, integrating it into educational and dissemination activities, including curriculum design and public engagement, is crucial for effectively training future generations of researchers and innovators. Adopting an inclusive approach that also considers intersecting social categories such as ethnicity, age, or disability is key to producing excellent research that benefits all citizens. Neglecting this aspect of research not only compromises lives but also incurs financial implications.

Numerous studies highlight the critical role of the gender and/or dimension in our research areas². Historically, drug development has followed a 'one size fits all'

¹ [Analyzing How Sex and Gender Interact | Gendered Innovations \(stanford.edu\)](#)

² [Waxman DJ, Celenza JL. Genes Dev. 2003;17:2607–13](#)

model, primarily testing drugs on males, from pre-clinical research in rodents to clinical trials with limited female participation. As a result, women often report more adverse, and sometimes fatal, side effects compared to men (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Women tend to have smaller body size and more fat tissue than men, which affects drug distribution, and smaller kidneys, which leads to slower drug elimination. Liver enzymes may behave differently because of oral contraception and some hormone therapy. Women's heart rhythms are different from men's (longer QT interval), which makes women more susceptible to fatal heart disturbances, called arrhythmias. © Sabine Oertelt-Prigione.

All gender equality aspects and measures to be taken into account during grant preparation and project management must be included in a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)**, which is a set of commitments and actions that aim to promote gender equality in an organisation through a process of structural change.

With Horizon Europe, the Commission reaffirms its commitment to gender equality in research and innovation, elevating it as a cross-cutting priority and introducing reinforced provisions (see section 3). It further aligns with international initiatives, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, which emphasize the importance of promoting gender equality and ensuring universal access to healthcare and well-being³. Furthermore, in MSCA programmes, the principles of the **European Charter for Researchers** and **Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers** are also a cornerstone to develop and manage the projects.

³ [Gender equality in research and innovation \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/infographic/infographic_gender_equality_in_research_and_innovation.pdf)

2.2. Gender equality and dimension integration in RBP-ReguNet project

The project's objective is to identify unconventional RBPs and discover novel potential therapeutic targets for untreatable conditions, such as cancer, neurological disorders, liver diseases, and infectious diseases, where the critical role of gender and sex dimorphism has been already confirmed. RBP-ReguNet promotes interdisciplinary collaboration, aiming to equip the next generation of researchers with the necessary skills to drive advancements in RBP biology and therapeutic development. The project will provide comprehensive scientific training to 11 doctoral candidates (DC), covering computational, structural, molecular, and cellular biology, as well as medicinal chemistry and pharmacological screening.

One of the excellence criteria outlined in the MSCA-2021-DN-01-01 call was the 'Soundness of the proposed methodology' which includes interdisciplinary approaches, consideration of the gender dimension, and other relevant diversity aspects for the research project, as well as the quality of open science practices. In this context, by actively integrating the gender and sex dimensions into the RBP-ReguNet project, our aim is to contribute to ongoing global efforts, showcasing our commitment to evidence-based research that takes into account the diverse needs and realities of individuals. By incorporating the gender dimension into our project, we acknowledge and address the differences, experiences, and needs of individuals from different genders. This integration enables us to develop a more comprehensive understanding of health and disease, design improved research methodologies, and obtain more applicable real-world data.

This deliverable presents a comprehensive guideline and intersectional research planning scaffold for integrating the gender and sex dimension into our HORIZON-MSCA-DN project. The plan is designed to ensure that our research is conducted in a manner that respects and acknowledges gender differences, addresses gender biases, and promotes inclusivity and equity. By implementing this plan, we aim to generate knowledge that is more robust, relevant, and applicable to diverse populations, while contributing to the broader vision of gender equality in biomedical research endorsed by the European Commission (see section 4).

3. EU framework for gender equality and gender dimension integration

Sex and gender are fundamental determinants of the organisation of life and society. Therefore, recognising and taking these differences into account is essential in scientific knowledge creation and should be reflected in research funding programmes, R&I content, and outreach and dissemination activities. The aim of the new framework is to enhance the European research and innovation system, foster gender-equal working environments where all talents can flourish and integrate the gender dimension more effectively into projects to enhance research quality, as well as the societal relevance of the knowledge, technologies, and innovations generated. This approach supports the broader goal of achieving gender equality and reducing health disparities, ultimately leading to a fairer and more equitable society. There are **three main levels** at which gender equality is addressed in Horizon Europe:

A. **Having a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in place** is advisable (mandatory in Horizon Europe 2022 calls and onwards, or in case the legal entities applying for funding does not have an equivalent document). As detailed in the General Annexes to Horizon Europe 2021-2022 work programme, to comply with the eligibility criterion, a GEP must meet some mandatory requirements (Figure 2):

- a. **Be a public document:** The GEP should be a formal document signed by the top management and disseminated within the institution. It should demonstrate a commitment to gender equality, set clear goals and detailed actions and measures to achieve them.
- b. **Have dedicated resources:** Resources for the design, implementation, and monitoring of GEPs may include funding for specific positions such as Equality Officers or Gender Equality Teams as well as earmarked working time for academic, management and administrative staff.
- c. **Include arrangements for data collection and monitoring:** GEPs must be evidence-based and founded on sex or gender-disaggregated baseline data collected across all staff categories. This data should inform the GEP's objectives and targets, indicators, and ongoing evaluation of progress, and be reported on annually.
- d. **Be supported by training and capacity-building:** Actions should address gender equality and unconscious gender biases, and may include developing gender competence establishing working groups dedicated to specific topics and raising awareness through workshops and communication activities.

Figure 2. Minimum process-related requirements (building blocks) for an Integrated Gender Dimension Plan.

B. Incorporating a **gender dimension** into research and innovation content is a default requirement and evaluated under the excellence criterion, unless the topic description explicitly specifies otherwise. The gender dimension cuts across all aspects of Horizon Europe and contributes to numerous steps in the R&I cycle, ranging from disclosing the sex of cells in experiments to considering the needs of women, men, and gender-diverse individuals as end-users of technological innovations.

C. Promoting **gender balance** throughout the program is another objective, with a target of 50% representation of women on Horizon Europe-related boards, expert groups, and evaluation committees. Additionally, gender balance among research teams is established as a ranking criterion for proposals with identical scores.

Gender considerations are often overlooked or subject to bias in research, while research institutions and higher education tend to neglect the importance of incorporating sex and gender perspectives into the training of future professionals. This oversight results in a lack of sex- and gender-sensitive approaches in scientific knowledge and innovation, ultimately impacting the quality of research outcomes and the technologies derived from them.

Figure 3. Gender-sensitive research takes a twin approach: it pays attention to the participation of women and men, providing equal opportunities for all, and it integrates gender into the research content all the way from the initial research idea to the dissemination of results⁴.

⁴ [GEAR Tool](#)

A notable example is the predominant use of male animals in preclinical drug research, which hinders the generalization of findings to the broader population. Embracing the inclusion of the sex/gender dimension implies considering differences, whether they are biological or social, in both research and teaching practices (Figure 3).

The knowledge we generate forms the foundation upon which future generations build their societies. Therefore, it is crucial that the knowledge created through research and transmitted through education remains free from gender bias⁵.

In the context of bottom-up work program components, such as the European Research Council's calls and the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions calls under Pillar I of Horizon Europe, it is especially important to integrate the gender dimension throughout the entire research and innovation (R&I) cycle (Figure 3). Doing so ensures that sex and gender analysis is considered in the design and outcomes of research and teaching activities, mitigating biases, and resulting in more comprehensive and complete research outcomes. It further empowers researchers to challenge gender norms and stereotypes, encouraging a re-evaluation of standards and reference models. This approach fosters a deep understanding of the needs, behaviours, and attitudes of both genders, enhancing the societal relevance of the knowledge, technologies, and innovations produced. Additionally, it contributes to the development of goods and services that are better suited to potential markets.

⁵ [Integration of the sex/gender dimension into research and teaching content | European Institute for Gender Equality \(europa.eu\)](#)

4. Gender equality in RBP-ReguNet

As stated at the beginning of this document, gender, and more specifically sex, is a critical variable to be taken into account in the RBP-ReguNet research scope. There are plenty of examples where incorporating the gender dimension variable in our biomedical research is essential. The prevalence and severity of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) are higher in men than in women during the reproductive age. However, after menopause, NAFLD occurs at a higher rate in women, suggesting a protective role of estrogen⁶. Melanoma, another model system under consideration in this proposal, exhibits a higher incidence in men than in women, with variations related to ethnicity, age, and, most importantly, sex and gender⁷. Patients with melanoma or lung cancer, who receive checkpoint inhibitors as treatment, also exhibit sex-dependent response differences, with a higher proportion of male patients achieving successful remission compared to female patients⁸. The SARS-CoV2 pandemic has further underscored the urgent need to incorporate sex and gender analysis into research and innovation processes. Current global statistics demonstrate a higher mortality rate among men due to acute infection, while women are projected to experience more health, economic, and social consequences in the long term⁹. Additionally, several studies highlight differences between males and females in myelin disorders within the peripheral nervous system¹⁰. Integrating sex and gender analysis into research can unlock opportunities for discovery and innovation.

The aforementioned data snapshot clearly indicates that the gender and/or sex dimension could have a meaningful impact on our research program for RBP-ReguNet. It has the potential to offer fresh perspectives, raise new questions, and, importantly, promote social equality by ensuring that research findings are relevant to all segments of society.

4.1. Gender balance in RBP-ReguNet consortium

RBP-ReguNet gathers together 8 beneficiary partners and 7 associated partners from 5 European member countries and 1 associated state (UK?). A general overview on the gender balance at the partner institutions shows that most have a percentage of female employees higher than 50%, and all beneficiary partners have already a gender policy in place (Table 1).

Table 1. Gender balance and GEP implementation within RBP-ReguNet partners.

Partner	Gender of Scientist in Charge	% of women	% of men	% of gender-neutral persons	Gender policy in place
Beneficiaries					
1. USC	Both	57.7	42.3	NA	YES
2. Institut Curie	Man	60	40	NA	YES

⁶ [Lonardo et al., *Hepatology*, 2019; 70\(4\): 1457–1469](#)

⁷ [M. Bellenghi et al., *Cancers \(Basel\)*, 2020; 12\(7\): 1819](#)

⁸ [Conforti, F. et al. *Lancet Oncol*; 2018; 19, 737–746](#)

⁹ GlobalHealth5050. (2020). <https://globalhealth5050.org/>

¹⁰ [Francis B. Panosyan, *Neurology* 2017, 89 \(9\) 927-935](#)

3. Fundació Centre de Regulació Genòmica	Both	47	53	NA	YES
4. Stichting Sanquin Bloedvoorziening	Woman	71	29	NA	YES
5. IMMAGINA BioTechnology SRL	Man	40	60	NA	YES
6. Università Degli Studi Di Trento	Man	27.5	72.5	NA	YES
7. Università degli Studi di Milano	Man	45.8	54.2	NA	YES
8. European Molecular Biology Laboratory	Man	48	52	NA	YES
Associated Partners					
University of Glasgow	Man	51	49	NA	YES ¹¹
Fundación Kertor	Woman	50	50	NA	YES
Ribonexus	Man	NA	NA	NA	YES
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Woman	47	53	NA	YES ¹²

As depicted in the above tables, the RBP-ReguNet entire consortium shows a slightly unbalanced distribution of genders at a managing level, with a 35.7% of women Scientists in Charge of the RBP-ReguNet project while 64.5% are men. Regarding the Associated Partners management, that percentage equals, with both genders occupying half of the roles in charge.

4.2. Gender Equality Plans in the Consortium

4.2.1. University of Santiago de Compostela (Coordinator)

The university of Santiago de Compostela (USC) has already set up an Equality Plan, designed to be implemented throughout the entire institution¹³. The plan is organised in **6 main action areas**: Institutional culture; Teaching, research and transfer; Presence, promotion and representation; Co-responsible conciliation; Bullying and gender-based violence; and Socio-health conditions at work. For each of these areas, general and specific objectives have been established, as well as the actions necessary for the achievement of them. In total the Plan contains **9 general objectives**, 21 specific and 85 actions plans. Each of these actions is associated with indicators that allows to conduct evaluations of the implementation of the Plan. In addition, the Plan contains the units responsible for the execution of the different actions, involving the entire institution in an exercise of co-responsibility in the execution of the Plan.

The main objectives included in the USC's GEP more closely related to this project are General Objective 1, covering actions on **institutional commitment to**

¹¹ [University of Glasgow - MyGlasgow - Equality & Diversity](#)

¹² [CNR GEP](#)

¹³ [USC GEP](#)

equality; General Objective 2, covering **gender dimension in teaching, research and knowledge transfer**; General Objective 4, which sets up the foundations for **equal professional opportunities**; and General Objective 7, covering **equal conciliation of responsibilities**.

4.2.2. Beneficiary partners

4.2.2.1. Institut Curie

Institut Curie has since 2022 a new Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Plan (GEDIP) in place to actively implement organisational change and embed gender equality, diversity & inclusion into the Research Centre's processes and work environment¹⁴. It is meant to boost their positive track record on gender equality while offering good career opportunities to women. It also guides the institute in paying attention to other categories of inequality and how they can be compounded when different characteristics intersect through a comprehensive action plan.

Figure 4. Percentage of personnel by gender in 2018, 2019 and 2020 at Institut Curie. Source: Institut Curie GEDIP.

It pursues a series of objectives, including (1) the development of policies based on data and evidence, (2) the promotion of a fair and inclusive organisational culture, (3) to support a beneficial work-life balance, (4) to foster inclusive leadership and decision making, (5) to be an inclusive equal opportunities employer while (6) ensuring equality in career progression, (7) to support staff to integrate the sex and gender dimension into their research, and (8) prevent and combat harassment including gender-based violence

4.2.2.2. CRG

The Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Plan of the CRG¹⁵ is the result of the firm conviction and commitment on the part of the centre to collaborate in favour of a more just, tolerant, diverse and egalitarian society between women and men, which favours their advancement and development, and in which fundamental rights are respected and promoted. It also responds to our national and international regulatory framework on equality.

The current GEP, which is organized in **9 strategic axis and 4 plans**, is structured around two aspects:

- A. Strategic: from which the centre promotes equality, diversity and inclusion, following 4 global sustainable development goals:

¹⁴ [Institut Curie GEP](#)

¹⁵ [CRG GEP](#)

1. Health & Wellness
 2. Gender equality
 3. Reduction of inequalities
 4. Alliances to achieve the objectives (CERCA Centres, EU-LIFE, among others)
- B. Operational: from which a set of measures that make up a coherent framework and that respond to the reality and needs in terms of equality, diversity and inclusion of the centre are integrated.

The CRG is also the coordinator of the H2020 project LIBRA, promoting gender equality in research and innovation. Already since 2013 CRG established the Gender Balance Committee, which is currently implementing the Gender Equality Plan to achieve institutional changes. Furthermore, a “Women in Science Support Grant” and mentoring programme for Postdocs have been launched and are running already in the fourth and second edition, respectively.

4.2.2.3. SANQUIN

Sanquin's Gender Equality Plan is published on their website¹⁶ and is evaluated and updated annually. Policies with respect to diversity in general are being developed. Sanquin intends to create a more explicit connection between its external diversity policy and its internal diversity and inclusivity policy. The emphasis is not only on gender, but on creating an inclusive organization in which employees feel welcome.

Sanquin Research is home to around 250 research employees, including around 70 PhD students, 50 post-docs and 30 group leaders of which about half are full professors. The 2021 annual report of the Sanquin Blood Supply Foundation states a total number of personnel of 2137, of which 71% is female. For the research division this is 256 people of which 63% is female.

A number of important actions on tackling gender equality issue are already in place for both female and male researchers, including training for both young and established personnel with respect to personal development and related skills. The plan states a number of actions already to be taken, with focus on increasing the number of women in higher positions, and to safe and social working environment.

4.2.2.4. IMMAGINA

Immagina Biotechnology is firmly committed to fostering an environment free from any form of discrimination based on gender, marital status, race, religion, colour, age, disability, or sexual orientation. Their primary focus is on evaluating every employee and potential candidate solely based on their merits, qualifications, and ability to excel in their respective roles.

At present, the Immagina Biotechnology dedicated team comprises 15 permanent members, with 6 of them being female professionals. In their forthcoming expansion, they are committed to provide equitable opportunities for both women and men to seek and secure these new positions, including executive and managerial roles. By nurturing a culture of fairness and

¹⁶ [Sanquin GEP](#)

advancement, the company aim to not only advance but also set a standard for progressive practices in the industry.

4.2.2.5. UniTN

Over the years, the University of Trento has adopted a wide range of measures to support gender equality, process that led to the adoption of its own GEP¹⁷. On a broader level, the adoption of a GEP that strongly promotes gender mainstreaming in research benefits most of all the research activity itself, contributes to the work of researchers by raising awareness on gender bias, facilitates the availability of goods and services that better meet the needs of a market that is made up of different individuals. Furthermore, the adoption of a gender perspective in R&I contributes to the implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals, not only in gender equality, but in a general way across all areas.

The GEP is in line with the strategies identified by the European Union to overcome gender asymmetries in science: **Fixing the numbers of women; fixing the institutions; and fixing the knowledge**. It also outlines the objectives that the GEP of the University of Trento aims to achieve and which guide the entire action plan:

1. Work-life balance, health, safety, well-being in light of differences; culture and well-being in the organization.
2. Gender balance in senior management positions and decision-making bodies.
3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.
4. Integrating the gender dimension in research and education.
5. Combating gender-based violence, workplace bullying, harassment and sexual harassment.

4.2.2.6. UMIL

The GEP of the University of Milan integrates with the **University's Gender Balance and the Positive Action Plan**¹⁸. The document incorporates the guidelines of the European Commission, and the indications of the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) aimed at identifying and implementing innovative strategies to promote cultural change and promote equal opportunities in Universities and Research Centres. The document consists of summary sheets of the objectives relating to the **6 "Key Areas"** identified, for each of which the actions, the direct and indirect target, the institutional and operational managers, the dedicated human and financial resources, the output, the outcome, the deadlines and the evaluation indicators are described. In addition, for each action, the relevance to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the UN 2030 Agenda was reported.

4.2.2.7. EMBL

In 2021, EMBL created the Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) Office along with the establishment of new EDI Governance structures. The EDI Office led the

¹⁷[UniTn GEP](#)

¹⁸[UNIMI GEP](#)

development of EMBL's first Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy 2022-2026 which was launched in December 2021. The current EMBL GEP¹⁹ draws from EMBL's wider Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Strategy which envisions a more inclusive research and work culture that leverages diversity, in its broadest sense, to enhance EMBL's role as a leader in the life sciences in Europe and globally.

Figure 5 Percentage of personnel by gender total in 2020. Source: EMBL GEP.

Overall, the gender split at EMBL across 2020 was 48% female, 52% male. The EMBL GEP's Action Plan is structured in 4 Axis that aim to guide all its structure:

Axis 1: Attract, develop, support and Promote Gender Equality;

Axis 2: Ensure that Gender Equality principles are built into all internal processes, systems and policies;

Axis 3: Develop a model of Inclusive Leadership and Gender Equality in science and our services;

Axis 4: Leverage Gender Equality best practices to positively influence our environment.

4.2.3. Associated partners

All associated partners have Equality and Diversity Policies in place or are publicly committed to promoting and implementing equality of opportunity in the learning, teaching, research and working environments.

¹⁹[EMBL GEP](#)

5. Plan for the integration of gender and sex dimension in RBP-ReguNet

Since all involved partners already have an established institutional GEP, and there is a tailored Career Development Plan for each DC that will be developed once they are recruited (detailed in Deliverable 5.1), **we have focused our efforts on the development of a plan oriented to sex dimension integration in the research cycle.** Sex has historically been ignored as an explanatory variable; therefore, literature searches may underplay its importance. However, the absence of pilot data should encourage, rather than discourage, including and analysing the sex variable. Sex has already been linked to numerous biological and physiological differences and to specific health outcomes, thus it is an essential variable to consider in developing our scientific hypotheses^{20,21,22}. In the **'Gendered Innovations 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation'** policy report²³ produced by an EU-funded H2020 expert group, suggest a series of questions to address when developing research hypotheses within the new Horizon Europe programme: Should sex be considered a co-variate, a confounder or an explanatory variable? How will it be possible to identify potential sex differences without overstating them? What is the biological plausibility of sex emerging as an important variable in this research question? Which intersecting factors such as age or hormonal status, should be considered?

The **Project Management Committee**, with the support of all partners, have formulated a Plan for the Integration of **Gender Dimension and Other Diversity Aspects**, with special emphasis in sex dimension. This plan will serve as the framework for our research program, based on the 'Gendered innovation 2' guidelines from Tenenbaum and colleagues, on the materials available at GE Academy²⁴ and in other official material available at EU repositories. We will address the gender, and specially sex dimension at every stage of the research cycle, starting from the initial research idea and extending to the dissemination of results, while meeting the **SMART principles** (specific, measurable, attainable, realistic, and time-related).

5.1. Intersectional approach

It is essential to take an intersectional approach when setting research priorities, developing hypotheses and formulating study designs. This approach can better predict variations in health outcomes and determine user needs, and ultimately lead to more inclusive, and solid research and engineering solutions^{25,26}. Apart

²⁰ Montgomery, C. H. and Sherif, K. *Journal of Women's Health and Gender-Based Medicine*, 2000; 9(5), 529–536

²¹ [Moerman, C., Deurenberg, R. and Haafkens, J. *BioMed Central Medicine*, 2009; 9\(1\)](#)

²² Oertelt-Prigione et al., *BioMed Central Medicine*, 2010; 8, 70–80

²³ [Gendered innovation 2: How inclusive analysis contributes to research and innovation \(europa.eu\)](#)

²⁴ [ge-academy.eu – ge-academy](#)

²⁵ Faulkner, W. (2004), *Strategies of Inclusion: Gender and the information society (SIGIS) report*, University of Edinburgh Press, Edinburgh.

²⁶ Weber, L. and Fore, M. (2007), *Handbook of Sociology and Racial and Ethnic Relations*, Springer Press, New York, pp. 191–219.

from gender and sex there also are multiple factors that may affect research and should be considered from the very beginning of our research design. Disabilities, ethnicity, race, age, geographic location, socioeconomic status, nationality, sexual orientation, lifestyle, environment, genetics, sex hormones, reproductive status, body composition, comorbidities, or body size are some of those factors (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Key aspects to consider through the entire research cycle when analysing sex in biomedical research. Source: *GENDERED INNOVATIONS 2: How Inclusive Analysis Contributes to Research and Innovation Report*.

During the **Research Idea Phase**, a comprehensive assessment of the existing knowledge in the field will be conducted. The formulation of hypotheses shall draw upon prior research and available literature. Undoubtedly, the body of knowledge regarding gender issues has steadily expanded over the past few decades, offering valuable reference material for the development of novel hypotheses in future research endeavours. During the **Research Proposal and Implementation Phase**, we will articulate research questions that are sensitive to gender considerations, carefully select methodologies that account for gender, and gather and analyse data in a manner that is attuned to gender nuances. In the **Dissemination Phase**, the data shall be reported and its impact on the research field examined, while ensuring that its dissemination in all our

publications and/or dissemination activities adheres to a gender-sensitive approach.

A. Identify the problem, specify research focus, and formulate hypotheses

The first step where sex considerations must be taken is during the early hypothesis formulation and when specifying the research focus. Specially in our field of interest, we must define if sex is a biological variable, and if such variable is significant for the study. Factors mediating sex background with the mechanism object of study, or disease, must be identified and classified.

An example on COVID-19's sex and gender modulating factors is displayed in Figure 7. Every study of COVID-19 must integrate sex as a biological variable. This includes using female and male cells and animal models in drug discovery and development, as well as using women and men in clinical trials. Females seem to develop side effects to medications more frequently than males, and all drug and vaccine trials for COVID-19 should include sex-specific analyses²⁷.

SEX AND GENDER AS POSSIBLE MODULATORS OF COVID-19

Figure 7. Sex and gender as possible modulators of COVID-19. © Sabine Oertelt-Prigione

B. Research design

Figure 8 represents a decision tree that we will use in our analysis of sex in our research program. We will implement a range of methodologies to integrate the gender dimension in our research protocols. Our studies involve functional and mechanistic assays using genetic manipulation and drugs in in vitro and in vivo models, and for this, we will follow recommendations in the Gendered Innovations 2 report guidelines (Figure 6).

²⁷ [Obias-Manno et al., 2007, Journal of Women's Health, 16\(6\), 807-817](#)

Figure 8. This decision tree represents a cognitive process for analysing sex. A 'no' indicates no further analysis is necessary. A 'yes' suggests the next step that should be considered.

Such recommendations involve several variables to consider and report within the research design and implementation, and should be tailored to the specific research model and objectives.

1. **Study type:** Different types of studies (cross-sectional/longitudinal, with/without controls, factorial designs, etc.) should be considered depending on the impact of sex differences in the results. Age and/or sex stratification, oversampling, hormonal/drug conditioning, or matching criteria are tools that must be taken into account.
2. **Study protocol:** Sex-dependent aspects should be explicitly addressed. If hormones are going to be measured, will circadian rhythms be taken into account, or metabolic differences are to be measured? Is there a contingency plan if sex differences make an intervention difficult? All these variables could affect data collection and induce to biased conclusions if not considered correctly.
3. **Statistical requirements:** The fundamental requirement for statistical analysis is an adequately large sample and an appropriate number of outcomes to guarantee power for the subsequent analysis. For sex-specific research this means including adequate numbers of female and male subjects. Including both sexes does not necessarily mean doubling the group size overall, as factorial designs (progressing from a T-test to an

analysis of variation) reduce the sample size increase from doubling to about a 50 % increase²⁸.

4. **Practical and logistical factors:** The availability of models or samples for both sexes, or facilities set up to accommodate sex-specific experiments or groups are variables to be considered during the research design.

Another example from Tannerbaum *et al.* (2017) shown in Figure 9²⁹ highlights the essential information that must be collected and how with regards to sex and age along the entire R&D cycle of drug development, from discovery to post-marketing trials. It is essential that female and male systems must be included from early cell models and analysed separately.

Additionally, continuing with the intersectional approach, age and genetic ancestry, as long as pregnancy, should also be taken into account, as these characteristics may affect drug efficacy, safety and toxicity and have a great impact in patients' lives³⁰.

Figure 9. Sex and age considerations in drug development and testing. Source: Tannenbaum *et al.* (2017).

²⁸ [Buch, T.C., et al. 2019; Journal of Molecular Medicine, 97, 871-877.](#)

²⁹ [Tannenbaum C., Day D. & Matera Alliance, Pharmacological Research, 2017; 121, 83-93](#)

³⁰ [Dandara, C., et al. Lancet Oncology, 2014; 19\(6\), 737- 746](#)

Therefore, since that cell, tissue and animal models will be the main biological models in RBP-ReguNet project, we have outlined some variables and measurements to take into account during **research design and implementation**:

In vitro experiments

- a. Report the genetic sex of human or animal cells lines and cultured cells
- b. Compare male and female cells
- c. Record the age of the donor
- d. Document the growth conditions and number of passages of all cell lines and cultured cells
- e. Add oestrogen or testosterone to cells to determine effect

Animal experiments

- a. Report the sex and age of the animals
- b. Include both sexes in animal experiments
- c. Include pregnant animals
- d. Analyse results separately for male and female animals
- e. Explore the possible sex/age differences using small stratified samples
- f. Use a factorial design to independently assess the effect of sex/ age
- g. Consider the role of gonadal hormones across the age span

Compliance with these requirements is mandatory when feasible and pertinent. Otherwise, a solid justification based on experimental or consolidated data is required.

C. Collect data

Sex definition must be prespecified to avoid any misconception during collection and data analysis. From such starting point, it is essential to confirm the genetic make-up of all cells. Analysing sex in cell samples requires obtaining reliable and up-to-date information about the cell's genetics, since it can change after years in culture, and specially in works involving cell reprogramming.

Regarding human research participants or samples, if that is the case, reporting the sex of the research subject is important even in single-sex studies, to allow meta-analysis, in order to identify research gaps and prevent overgeneralising findings beyond the sex studied. Furthermore, will sex be conceptualised as binary? When working with very large datasets, the likelihood of including individuals with differences in sex development/intersex could be significantly high, which means that some data will not fit into a prespecified binary sex classification. In such cases, researchers should define how they want to address this issue before data collection. Data from these individuals should not be simply labelled as outliers and disregarded.

D. Analyse data

When analysing data, sex is a crucial variable for understanding the sex differences observed and should be considered and reported. Furthermore, sex-disaggregated results permit a more comprehensive vision of the results and future meta-analysis. Researchers should consider that differences within groups of females and males may be more significant than differences between the groups. Also, factors intersecting with sex or individual variations in biological and sociocultural factors throughout a person's life can greatly influence the

manifestation of various traits. Simply comparing means may restrict the real-world relevance of research findings and make sex dimension a confounder instead an explanatory variable³¹.

E. Reporting results

Detailed reporting of experimental design is crucial for ensuring reproducibility. Researchers should disclose the absence of sex differences in their analyses to mitigate publication bias, which is particularly important in meta-analyses. In cases where data on sex differences are inconclusive, especially when related to intersecting factors, researchers should make a note of it.

F. Dissemination of results

Dissemination strategies will take into account the complexity of target audiences and will not restrict the target audience to academic peers. An intersectional approach will sensitise the researcher to many other potential audiences. The Communication and Dissemination Committee will coordinate the actions to be taken in this regard, where a portfolio of potential audiences will be developed and reached.

5.2. Training

There is abundant available training online material for researchers and academics on how to include the gender dimension into research design and teaching curricula. Horizon Europe ecosystem, handbooks developed by expert groups, European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), or other projects focused on gender and sex dimension in research are sources of useful information, including webinars, tutorials, tools, and template documents.

Below we outline the collected resources and planned activities focused on the gender and sex dimension integration to be carried out along the project.

5.2.1. Training material

5.2.1.1. Gender Equality Strategy Monitoring Portal

The [GENDER EQUALITY STRATEGY Monitoring Portal \(europa.eu\)](https://europa.eu/gender-equality-strategy-monitoring-portal) is a web-based platform that aims to facilitate the access and analysis of data related to the progress and challenges of the Gender Equality Strategy. The portal provides various indicators and statistics that reflect the current situation and trends of gender equality in different domains, such as education, employment, health, violence, and decision-making. The portal is intended to serve as a useful resource for policy makers, researchers, stakeholders, and anyone interested in gender issues, as it allows them to monitor the implementation and impact of the strategy, identify areas of strength and improvement, and compare the developments over time.

Below there is an example of the data available at the portal and the types of visualization and material the researchers can extract from it (Figure 10).

³¹ [Bale, T., Epperson, C. Sex as a Biological Variable: Who, What, When, Why, and How. *Neuropsychopharmacol* 42, 386–396 \(2017\).](#)

Figure 10. Women among members of boards of research funding organisations (2022). Source: GENDER EQUALITY STRATEGY Monitoring Portal.

5.2.1.2. Fighting Gender Stereotypes

As part of the intersectional approach we are taking, it is also essential to highlight the importance of fighting gender stereotypes. From the conceptualization of researchers to the research design. The following two online repositories of resources and toolkits from European Commission will function as a reference for gathering information, and preventing and solving any potential conflicts during the project.

[Educational toolkits to help fight gender stereotypes \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-room/default.aspx?id=14112)

[End Gender Stereotypes \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-room/default.aspx?id=14112)

5.2.1.3. GENDERACTION+ Project

The *Gender Equality Network to Develop ERA Communities To coordinate Inclusive and sustainable policy implementation (GENDERACTION+)* Project aims to improve, coordinate, and promote new policies towards gender equality and overcome geographic inequalities in the EU. The network aims to develop policy solutions to increase excellence and social responsibility of knowledge through the integration of the gender dimension in research, innovation and teaching. In such regard, the project has made available useful material, such as templates, deliverables, toolkits, or webinars ([Webinar: Gender Dimension in Research and Innovation \(GiRI\)](#)) that will be an important source of information for our own project.

5.2.1.4. European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)

Among multiple other initiatives, the institute have developed, updated and maintained the GEAR Tool, a toolkit for learning, training, and developing

documents related to gender equality matter such this deliverable. It will serve as a reference for future updates on the plan and new related documents.

[Publications and Resources | European Institute for Gender Equality \(europa.eu\)](#)

[Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool | European Institute for Gender Equality \(europa.eu\)](#)

5.2.2. Training activities

The Management and Training Committees will organise a line-up of dynamic and involving activities for the DCs to widen and consolidate gender equality and sex dimension integration notions and tips. The following contents and activities will be integrated and developed during the training and transferable skills courses established during the project.

- A. Scientific Literature Review: Conduct a comprehensive literature review on the sex differences in relevant biomedical research areas, identifying key studies and their implications for experimental design and analysis where sex variable is particularly critical.
- B. Case Studies Discussion: Present case studies from the literature where overlooking the sex dimension has led to biased or inconclusive results. Encourage students to critically analyse the impact of sex bias and discuss strategies to avoid such pitfalls.
- C. Seminar Series: Organize a seminar series featuring experts in the field of sex-based research. Speakers will share their experiences and insights on considering sex as a biological variable in biomedical research.
- D. Experimental Design Workshop: Conduct a workshop on experimental design, emphasizing the importance of including both male and female subjects in preclinical and clinical studies. Which strategies can be used to account for sex-based differences in study design.
- E. Data Analysis Tutorial: Organize a hands-on tutorial session on analysing data with a sex-based approach and demonstrate statistical techniques and tools used to assess and interpret sex differences in biomedical research data.
- F. Grant Writing Exercise: Assign students the task of writing a mock grant proposal that incorporates the sex dimension in their research. Provide feedback and guidance to improve their understanding and integration of this concept.
- G. Collaborative Projects: Facilitate collaborative projects among PhD students, where they work together to incorporate the sex dimension in their research, encouraging interdisciplinary collaborations to promote comprehensive investigations.
- H. Ethical Considerations Workshop: Organize a workshop focusing on the ethical considerations associated with studying sex differences in biomedical research and discuss the importance of informed consent, privacy, and participant safety.

These training activities will help PhD students develop a deep understanding of the importance of considering the sex dimension in biomedical research, equip them with the necessary skills for study design and analysis, and foster a collaborative and inclusive research environment.

Moreover, with the first Progress report, on month 13, the DCs will present a gender and sex dimension integration plan tailored to their research plans. The plans will be reviewed by the **Training/Doctoral studies Committee** to ensure a proper integration of such factors in the project.

5.2.3. Timeline

- Continuous formation – EU HE virtual symposia and webinars
- M8 (November 2023) – RBP-ReguNet Initial Meeting | Courses on Transferable Skills 1&2
- M18 (September 2024) – Course on Transferable Skills 3
- M24 (March 2025) – RBP-ReguNet Interim Meeting
- M30 (March 2025) – Courses on Transferable Skills 4 & 5
- M40 (June 2026) - RBP-ReguNet 2nd Meeting & International Conference | Final reports on DC's individual projects and career development plans

6. Conclusion

The Plan for the Integration of Gender Dimension and Other Diversity aspects, with special attention to sex factor aims to provide the Doctoral Candidates with the necessary training and tools for the correct integration of gender and specially sex dimension along the entire cycle of their research, in accordance with the highest standards of the Horizon Europe program objectives.

7. Deviations

The present deliverable was submitted on month 6 instead of on month 3 due to a delayed incorporation of the project's main project manager to the staff team, delays in the signature of the Consortium Agreement (CA), as well as an overall delay on the start of project activities. We do not expect this delay to impact the submission of other deliverables nor the progress of the DC's individual projects.